

Towards understanding customer co-creation experience for mass customization

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Can usability tests on web based MC co-creation tools lead to yet undiscovered UX related problems?

Abstract

Mass-Customization (MC) has been considered to answer diversifying customer needs and reshape the consumer product market. However, after about two decades of trials, MC has been largely far from success in practice. One of the major reasons for this is considered to be lack of user engagement with customized products and the customization process itself. Therefore, this draws the attention from what is provided to the customer to how it is provided. The user involvement in MC is in the form of co-creation and often done through online tools, also known as product configurators. In practice, these product configurators for MC fail frequently in sales conversion. This study investigates the experience for customers throughout the co-creation process in an attempt to shed a light on different aspects of this experience and provide a better understanding of all contributing factors.

Keywords: Mass-Customization · Co-creation · Product configurators · User Experience

Method

Based upon extensive literature review, six Mass-Customization Co-Creation tools were selected. To ensure each tool has proper merit to be analysed, three conditions were set. To optimize the search for new problems, the selected tools needed to have solved most basic and common problems found during the literature review. Secondly, only web based tools were selected. Thirdly, the selected tools needed to encapsulate a broad variety of categories, interaction styles and input methods. Each tool was tested with a sample size of five. Each participant was asked to perform only one of the MC co-creation tools. In total 30 participants were tested for the six selected tools, with each participant testing only one tool.

During the survey, both general and tool-specific open questions were conducted, as those were most likely to provide the research with yet undiscovered faults. Lastly, all participants were

A user testing the Care-Of personalized vitamin tool

asked to complete a closed question survey measured with a likert scale. The closed question survey created a way to indicate the weight of known faults in the current design of MC co-creation. It also gave the research leads towards some problems that might come with certain features. The results of the open questions were then used to further clarify the survey outcomes.

111 Knit by New Balance
With their 111 Knit, New Balance adapts a Hybrid Customization/Personalization style, powered by Unmade's digital knitting possibilities.

TMA1 by AIAIAI

AIAIAI offers customized headphone configurations, based upon your Spotify music preferences and listening data. The user can later further customize the suggested model.

Results

The feedback gathered through the open questions was used to interpret and assert the results of the survey, which was then reformulated into the final conclusion.

Creating a comfort zone by implementing familiar elements in the product configurator helps putting customers at ease and gain their trust.

The best results for a pleasant user interaction with a large amount of features, occurred when tools had a configurator flow with a mandatory order. A configuration with less features might give a pleasant user interaction as well, but heightens the chances of user dissatisfaction with the degree of customizability.

In regards to ease of use a high degree of control or expert suggestions resulted in a positive increase. However tools with large amounts of complexity have a strong negative influence because of user incompetence which results in a need to simplify interaction without taking away control.

In order to verify our results with greater certainty, a test case for a web based MC Co-Creation product could be drawn up.

Conclusion

The usability tests led to trajectories towards yet undiscovered problems. It also led to a better understanding of the relation between the different facets of user experience in web based Mass-Customization Co-Creation configurators.

In case of a low degree of customization the users did not like the final result because they could not express themselves and got bored quickly. In case of a high degree of customization the tools often got too advanced and complex. Users often got lost in the complexity and could not express themselves because using the tool was too challenging.

The challenge lies in the balancing act between the certain features (e.g.: simplicity and level of customization) not over committing to others (e.g.: level of self-expression).